

Readiness and Maturity Models for Industry 4.0: A Systematic Literature Review

Hüseyin Ünlü^a, Onur Demirörs^a and Vahid Garousi^b

^a*Izmir Institute of Technology, Izmir, Turkey*

^b*Queen's University, Belfast, UK*

{huseyinunlu, onurdemirors}@iyte.edu.tr, v.garousi@qub.ac.uk

Appendix

The maturity/readiness models reviewed in this study are summarized based on their characteristics in relation with type, focus, structure, research methodology followed during design, base frameworks, tool-support, community support, objectivity, and extent of usage in practice as follow:

A.1 Maturity and Readiness Model for Industry 4.0 Strategy (M1)

Akdil et al. [12] proposed an Industry 4.0 maturity model to provide companies a tool to help them understand their current state regarding Industry 4.0. The followed methodology during design is based on a literature review and also, they included some questions from the literature. The model contains 13 associated fields grouped in three dimensions such as smart products, and services, smart business processes and strategy, and organizations. Their assessment criteria are based on Industry 4.0 principles (real-time data management, interoperability, virtualization, decentralized, agility, service-oriented and integrated business processes) and technologies (adaptive robotics, data analytic, and artificial intelligence, simulation, embedded systems, communication and networking, cybersecurity, cloud, additive manufacturing, virtualization technologies, sensors and actuators, RFID, RTLS, and mobile technologies). They use a questionnaire-based survey to identify the maturity level of a company is given in the study. The evaluation includes 4 stages as "0-Absence", "1-Existence", "2-Survival" and "3-Maturity". In each field, the questions are weighted between 0-3 to calculate the maturity level. The maturity levels are calculated by the given equations. For each level in each associated dimension, they explain the company's level. They conducted the

proposed maturity model in a retail company. They calculated the maturity level based on the scores of the questionnaires. Although their study is applied in one of the companies, there is almost no clue about the usage of the model in practice and the authors do not mention any feedback from the field.

A.2 MOM/CMM (Manufacturing Operations Management / Capability Maturity Model) (M2)

MOM/CMM is created by MESA (Manufacturing Enterprise System Association) to determine the policy, procedure, and execution of a manufacturing operation management to be organized, robust, and repeatable [33]. The model covers 4 main process areas such as production operation management, inventory management, quality test operations, and management and maintenance operations management. In each process area, there are 8 different activities. These activities are evaluated between maturity levels 0 to 5. The model includes 832 weighted questions and the improvement strategies are based on the scored answers for these questions. They designed a questionnaire-based tool to help evaluate the maturity and readiness of manufacturing enterprises [57]. The tool which is Microsoft Excel Macro is self-guided. It offers two assessment modes: comprehensive and quick.

A.3 A Maturity Model for Assessing the Digital Readiness of Manufacturing Companies (DREAMY) (M3)

DREAMY [34] is a maturity model to assess a manufacturing company's readiness level for starting the digital transformation process and to identify strengths and weaknesses. Their model is inspired by the CMMI framework and it is to assesses 5 main process areas such as design and engineering, production management, quality management, maintenance management, and logistics management. There are 18 aspects of these groups. The maturity levels are inspired by CMMI and thus it has five-scale maturity levels from 1 to 5 (initial, managed, defined, integrated and interoperable, digital-oriented). The model assesses the digital readiness of manufacturing companies through four analysis dimensions such as process, monitoring and control, technology, and organization.

The assessment approach of the model is based on an interview. The model was validated with academia and company experts and a questionnaire (including 200 questions) was developed as an output of this validation. Each question in the questionnaire includes 5 normative answers (maturity level 1 to 5). Thus, they obtained
65 a standard scoring method.

They also proposed a methodology to guide manufacturing companies towards digitalization [58]. The methodology includes four steps: maturity assessment, strength and weakness identification, opportunities identification, and digital transformation roadmap definition. They applied this methodology in organizations to gather empirical
70 evidence from three case studies. They performed interviews with the companies and different process areas were assessed in each case. Their result shows that the identified strengths and weaknesses and opportunities were in line with the company's perceptions. The most interesting steps were the identification of strengths and weaknesses and suggested opportunities for the involved companies rather than
75 maturity indexes as they provide a guide on the possible steps to follow.

A.4 Three Stage Maturity Model in SME's towards Industry 4.0 (M4)

Ganzarain and Errasti. [19] proposed a three-stage maturity model to guide and train companies (SMEs) identifying new opportunities for diversification in areas within Industry 4.0. The model includes three stages such as envision, enable, and enact.
80 Envision stage includes capacity and resources analysis and understanding of Industry 4.0. The enable stage consists of identifying the requirements and identifying the technology that evolved in Industry 4.0. The last stage enact includes training capacity, risk management, and Industry 4.0 projects. The maturity scale of this model includes five levels: initial, managed, defined, transform, and detailed business model. The
85 model was analyzed firstly in the Basque Country with a representative sample of SMEs and a pilot study has been started but there is no information about the details and the result of the study.

A.5 Industry 4.0: Building the Digital Enterprise (M5)

Geissbauer et al. (PwC) [20] proposed a maturity model to assess the readiness of
90 the companies mainly in digitization. Their model consists of 4 maturity levels (digital

novice, vertical integrator, horizontal collaborator, and digital champion) and 7 dimensions (digital business models and customer access, digitization of product and service offerings, digitization and integration of vertical and horizontal value chains, data&analytics as a core capability, agile IT architecture, compliance, security, 95 legal&tax, organization, employees and digital culture). They also suggest companies create initial projects, define the capabilities they need, become a data virtuoso, transform into a digital enterprise, and actively plan an ecosystem approach upon the completion of the success in digitization. They included this model in their survey-based research conducted with over 2000 senior executives from industrial products 100 companies in 26 countries.

PwC also designed an online self-assessment tool [29] to identify the company's position regarding Industry 4.0. The tool allows companies to conduct self-assessment, identify their needs for action, and benchmark against others. The method of the self-assessment is based on a questionnaire and thus each dimension includes weighted 105 questions to assess the company. The tool asks the industry, country, annual revenue, and the scope for the assessment before the start. The first three dimensions are mandatory for the assessment but they suggest choosing all dimensions for the most comprehensive assessment result. The tool can be applied in many companies as it is an online self-assessment but there is no data about the usage in the practice of the tool.

110 *A.6 Industry 4.0-MM (M6)*

Gokalp et al. [14] proposed Industry 4.0-MM to evaluate the Industry 4.0 maturity level of a manufacturing company and help them to increase the economic benefits of Industry 4.0 by improving their maturity level. The model is inspired and based on Spice. The structure of the model is similar to Spice and the only difference is it includes 115 aspects instead of processes. The aspects of the model are categorized as Asset Management, Data Governance, Application Management, Process Transformation, and Organizational Alignment. It has 6 capability levels from 0 to 5 (incomplete, performed, managed, established, predictable, and optimizing). Each aspect is scored between these capability levels. The model is constructed based on a well-known 120 method but there is no case study conducted. Their future work includes conducting case studies to validate the applicability of the proposed model.

A.7 IMPULS Industry 4.0 Readiness (M7)

IMPULS Industry 4.0 Readiness Model [24] was designed to examine the Industry 4.0 readiness of the mechanical and plant engineering companies in Germany. Their model includes 18 fields grouped under 6 dimensions such as strategy and organization, smart factory, smart operations, smart products, data-driven services, employees. The capability of these dimensions is measured by 6 levels from 0 to 5. In this model, levels 0 and 1 indicate newcomers, level 2 indicates learners, and levels 3, 4, and 5 indicates leaders. Each dimension is ranked from 1 to 5 for each indicator, then the final value is obtained. Each indicator has a coefficient. They provide an online questionnaire as an assessment tool. This model was used to assess the Industry 4.0 Readiness of German manufacturing and mechanical and plant engineering companies. The result based on 234 mechanical and plant engineering and 602 manufacturing companies with more than 20 employees shows that the average readiness is 0.9 and 0.6 respectively. The size of the company is the most important successor of higher levels as it showed statistical significance in 5 dimensions. The survey also suggests action items for the newcomers and the learners.

IMPULS was also used as a readiness maturity model to assess the readiness of the organizations in Malaysian SMEs [59]. In this study, they invited 250 participants from Malaysia to respond to their questionnaire. They formed a formula to the way the dimension scores were based on the feedback of the survey participants asking the relative importance of each dimension in implementing Industry 4.0. They calculated the score and average of each dimension through the formula. Their result shows that Malaysian SMEs are lacking knowledge in terms of distribution control, data-driven services, smart factory and strategy, and organization.

A.8 An Overview of a Smart Manufacturing System Readiness Assessment (M8)

Jung et al. [21] proposed a model to assess a manufacturing company's readiness to improve its operational performance by employing data-intensive technologies. The assessment framework includes 3 steps: profile the current state, assess the current state and develop an improvement plan. The proposed SMSRL is based on Factory Design

and Improvement (FDI) reference-activity model. There are yes/no questions to be answered by the factory personnel (self-assessment) to profile the current state of the company. The questionnaire is categorized into 4 measurement dimensions such as
155 organizational maturity, IT maturity, performance management maturity, and information connectivity maturity. To evaluate the current state, the score of each dimension is calculated with different methods such as counting measure, activity maturity scoring scheme, incidence matrix-based similarity measure, and incidence scoring scheme. The activity maturity scoring scheme is based on CMMI. After
160 computing the scores, an improvement plan should be developed. However, there is no method to provide a more detailed recommendation and this is the future work of the study.

The proposed model is validated by testing the statistical significance between SMSRL and operational performance. Their results show that there are positive
165 correlations between SMSRL and operational performance, overall performance, and value-based performance. There is no detail about the usage in the practice of the model, excluding the validation.

A.9 A Smartness Assessment Framework for Smart Factories Using Analytic Network Process (M9)

170 Lee et al. [23] proposed a smartness assessment framework to assess the smartness of the factories and apply it in manufacturing companies. Their network model includes 10 sub-dimensions grouped under 4 main dimensions: leadership, performance, process, and system and automaton. This model was constructed in two phases: identifying the criteria based on literature review and consulting experts. First, they
175 calculated the initial weightings of the criteria consulting to the experts after they identified the list of criteria. Then, they used the analytic network process to identify the correlation between the assessment items. The model includes 5 maturity levels: checking, monitoring, control, optimization, and autonomy. The scoring is based on quantitative analysis.

180 For the validation and verification of the proposed model, they applied the framework to 20 companies in the Republic of Korea, with an average of 25.7 million dollars turnover. The manufacturing processes include casting, painting, assembling,

molding, and machining. Their result shows that applying the analytic network process to the assessment gives more precise results as they include the interdependencies
185 between criteria.

A.10 SIMMI 4.0 – A Maturity Model for Classifying the Enterprise-wide IT and Software Landscape Focusing on Industry 4.0 (M10)

Leyh et al. [30], [60] proposed a maturity model to classify a company's IT system landscape in the context of the Industry 4.0 requirements. The followed methodology
190 during design is based on a literature review and they inspired from two models: CMMI and CSOAMM[61]

. The model includes 4 dimensions such as vertical integration, horizontal integration, digital product development, and cross-sectional technology criteria. The maturity of the dimensions is evaluated with 5 stages: basic digitization, cross-
195 departmental digitization, horizontal and vertical digitization, full digitization, and optimized full digitization. The assessment approach is based on interviews or self-assessment and the scoring is qualitative.

This model only focuses on the technological aspects of Industry 4.0. However, organizational and environmental aspects are not considered. It is not validated or
200 applied in any company.

A.11 The Connected Enterprise Maturity Model (M11)

Rockwell Automation proposed "The Connected Enterprise Maturity Model" [27] to achieve significant reductions in costs and improved capabilities with an effective change in both technologies and organizational cultures. The proposed model consists
205 of 5 maturity stages such as assessment, secure and upgraded network, and controls, defined and organized working data capital (WDC), analytic, and collaboration. The assessment stage includes 4 dimensions: information infrastructure, control devices that feed and receive data, networks that move all the information, and security policies.

The model focuses on IT/OT companies. They designed this enterprise model
210 based on their experience in operations in 80 countries and 22000 employees. The model was applied in many companies including their partners such as Microsoft and Cisco. However, there is no detail about the result and assessment details.

A.12 A Maturity Model for Assessing Industry 4.0 Readiness and Maturity of Manufacturing Enterprises (M12)

215 Schumacher et al. [16] proposed a maturity model for assessing Industry 4.0
readiness by extending the dominating technology focus of recently developed models
by including organizational aspects. The model includes 9 dimensions: strategy,
leadership, customers, products, operations, culture, people, governance, and
technology. Each dimension includes a set of maturity items. Each item is evaluated
220 based on a questionnaire with answers reaching from 1 (not implemented) to 5 (fully
implemented). The questionnaire is transformed into a software-supported assessment
tool.

They measured the accuracy of the maturity model from the expert interviews.
123 questionnaires were sent to the practitioners and researchers. Based on the 23
225 responses, the model was rated 3.2 over 4 overall. Then, they calculated a weighting
factor for each maturity item based on the responses.

They also applied the model in two case studies in industrial enterprises and the
results obtained from one case study are included. They sent the questionnaire by email
to an Austrian manufacturing enterprise with around 400 employees that designs and
230 manufactures aerospace components and test equipment. The results show that the
lowest maturity level is in the strategy dimension and the highest was in products. The
collected feedback from the company shows that the clarity of the questionnaire,
transparency, and consistency of the tool, and understandability of the modes of
representation were positive.

A.13 Towards a Framework for Assessing the Maturity of Manufacturing Companies in Industry 4.0 Adoptions (M13)

235 Scremin et al. [17] proposed a framework to assess the Industry 4.0 maturity of
manufacturing companies that have already started to manufacture Industry 4.0. They
aim to understand the transformation process in manufacturing companies transitioning
240 to Industry 4.0 by the proposed framework. Their model is called Adoption Maturity
Model (AMM) that includes 3 axes such as strategy, maturity, and performance. Eight
indicators are categorized within these axes and a total of 30 maturity items are
categorized within these eight indicators.

The model was designed by completing several steps. Firstly, the model was
245 designed based on the literature review on Industry 4.0 and maturity models. Then, they
applied the model to 10 manufacturing companies from Italy and Canada. They created
an interview guide for data collection. They collected the data using this guide. The
case studies were analyzed and thresholds for each maturity item were determined.
Then, adoption maturity indicators were calculated and represented. They performed a
250 cross-case comparative analysis with the quantitative assessment and formed a
comparison matrix. Finally, they concluded on Industry 4.0 adoption. The case studies
also helped them to see the limitations of the proposed model.

A.14 Acatech Industrie 4.0 Maturity Index (MI4)

Schuh et al. [26] proposed a 6 staged maturity model to guide companies to
255 become learning, agile companies capable of continuous, agile adaptation to a changing
environment in Industry 4.0. The maturity stages consist of computerization,
connectivity, visibility, transparency, predictive capacity, and adaptability where each
stage provides additional benefits. In the model, the first two stages achieve digitization
and the remaining four stages achieve the goal of Industry 4.0. The model includes four
260 key areas such as resources, information systems, organization structure, and culture.
Each key area is assessed in every maturity stage. The key areas are also divided into
sub-dimensions. Their assessment approach is based on a questionnaire with multiple-
choice questions.

The model was created based on 4 steps including different case studies and
265 workshops with the contribution from both academia and industry. In the first step,
different projects from the partners were discussed. In the second step, they formed a
committee to review the project progresses. In the third step, the projects were validated
in terms of their applicability in a technology-based manufacturing enterprise. The last
step was performed every three steps as it includes the verification of the findings.

270 The applicability of the model was validated in different practical application
scenarios. The validation helped them to confirm the principles of the model. The
findings from the usage of the model show that the companies do not include the full
implication in their strategies. Also, most of the companies do not understand the key
aspects of Industry 4.0 and they isolate the measures instead of pursuing a common

275 goal. An example case study to validate the model in a company is also included. Their
model can be used to develop a tool and best practices to assist companies in managing
the transformation to Industry 4.0.

The application of the Acatech Industrie 4.0 Maturity Index covers three phases:
identifying the current Industry 4.0 development stage, capabilities to be required, and
280 identifying concrete measures [62]. They applied this methodology to 26 companies
and their plants. The application is based on a workshop at the plant and evaluation. In
the end, companies have received a roadmap with different measures to reach the upper
maturity level in all dimensions.

285 *A.15 The Degree of Readiness for the Implementation of Industry 4.0 (MI5)*

Pacchini et al. [45] proposed a model to measure the degree of readiness of a
manufacturing company in Industry 4.0. Their model is inspired by the structure of two
standards: Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) J4000 and Spice. They modified the
structure of SAE J4000 in the needs of Industry 4.0. The proposed model includes 4
290 levels: Level 0 (not present), Level 1 (incompletely implemented), Level 2 (almost fully
implemented), and Level 3 (fully implemented). To measure the readiness of a
company, they included 8 enabling technologies: big data, the internet of things, cloud
computing, autonomous robots, additive manufacturing, cyber-physical systems,
augmented reality, and artificial intelligence. The selection of these eight technologies
295 was confirmed upon the feedback from the 4 experts from academia, government, and
the sector.

The degree of readiness is calculated based on the scores that come from the
prerequisites of the enabling technology. Each level is associated with a point. Then,
the degree of readiness of a company (DR) is calculated. To evaluate how well an
300 organization is prepared to implement Industry 4.0, they used the Spice standard as a
basis.

The usage of the model in the real-world was tested in a case study. The company
selected for this case study was a multinational diesel engine manufacturer in Brazil
that employs around 1200 persons. The information from the company was gathered
305 with an interview organized between the two company employees and the researchers.

Then, the degree of readiness was calculated for each enabling technology and the degree of readiness of the company was calculated as 0.7569. The result shows that the company has a high degree of adaptation which is the advanced stage.

A.16 Smart Industry Maturity Index (MI6)

310 Smart Industry Maturity Index (SIRI) [46] was launched by the Singapore Economic Development Board in partnership with TÜV SÜD to help organizations assess existing manufacturing facilities and support them in Industry 4.0 transformation. The model was created based on a wide literature review on Industry 4.0 related concepts and frameworks. SIRI consists of three layers: 3 fundamental
315 building blocks of Industry 4.0 (process, technology, and organization), 8 pillars of focus, and 16 dimensions of assessment. These 16 dimensions are evaluated with an assessment matrix including 6 progressive bands (0-5) of maturity: undefined, defined, digital, integrated, automated, intelligent. Companies can evaluate their current digital maturity with the help of the Assessment Matrix.

320 SIRI was performed in 200 Singapore-based manufacturing companies that cover 12 manufacturing sectors. These companies range from small Singaporean enterprises to large, multinational corporations that originate from 14 different countries. They formed a report based on the assessment results. Lin et al [63] illustrated the methodology and processes for assessing 4 dimensions of SIRI such as operations,
325 automation, connectivity, and intelligence.

Singapore Government established the SIRI Assessor Program to recognize independent individuals who will assess the manufacturing companies using SIRI. This program is an important step to provide the objectivity of the assessment. The program covers both training and certification.

A.17 Smart Manufacturing Kaizen Level (MI7)

330 Smart Manufacturing Kaizen Level (SMKL) [47] aims to help the manufacturer improve its system implementation sustainably. It consists of two blocks: maturity and management. The maturity block includes 4 levels such as collecting, visualizing, analyzing, and optimizing. On the other hand, management block levels are installation
335 or worker, work station, factory, and supply chain. In their assessment matrix, each cell

indicates different maturity level productivity Kaizen which covers the integration of the system horizontally and vertically. They also performed a case study in a factory to illustrate automation productivity improvement by using SMKL.

A.18 The Smart Manufacturing Maturity Model for SMEs (M18)

340 Mittal et al. [48] proposed a maturity model for SMEs intending to support SMEs during the digital transformation towards smart manufacturing and Industry 4.0. They developed the model based on literature and critical review [15] and also interviews. The model consists of three axes: organizational dimensions, toolboxes, and maturity levels. There are 5 organizational dimensions: finance, people, strategy, process, and
345 product. Each dimension is also categorized into sub-dimensions. Maturity levels are identified as novice, beginner, learner, intermediate, and expert. There are also 7 toolboxes as the third axis such as fabrication/manufacturing tools, design, and simulation tools, robotics and automation tools, sensors and connectivity tools, cloud/storage tools, data analytic tools, and business management tools. The maturity
350 level of each toolbox is related to the required inputs or processes. They demonstrated two different case studies to see how the proposed toolboxes may be deployed. They obtained different maturity levels for the toolboxes identifying the required inputs. The model does not provide any tool-support.

A.19 A Maturity Assessment Approach for Conceiving Context-Specific Roadmaps in the Industry 4.0 Era (M19)

360 Colli et al. [49] proposed a maturity assessment approach based on Problem-Based Learning for structuring the assessment procedure as a dialectic process to facilitate the contextualization of the assessed company and thus provide improvement recommendations. The assessment approach includes a maturity model to assess the
360 company. The maturity model was created based on a literature review. There are 6 maturity levels (1-6): none, basic, transparent, aware, autonomous, integrated, and 5 dimensions: governance, technology, connectivity, value creation, competencies.

 Their assessment approach (360DMA) consists of 5 sequential stages: the creation of awareness, the definition of scope, data collection, evaluation and solution selection,

365 debriefing. Maturity assessment is performed in the data collection stage where a “self-
assessment” questionnaire consists of 25 multiple-answer questions addressing the six
maturity dimensions that are submitted to relevant stakeholders. The approach was
tested in three diverse industrial cases to assess digital maturity and suggest
improvement possibilities. The result of the assessment for the three cases was
370 transparent level but the recommendations for each case were different as a result of
different sectors of the companies.

A.20 Defining and Assessing Industry 4.0 Maturity Levels—Case of the Defence Sector (M20)

Bibby and Dehe [50] developed a model to measure the Industry 4.0 maturity of
375 a focal firm in the defense sector. The model includes 3 dimensions: factory of future,
people and culture, strategy. 13 key attributes are categorized under these dimensions.
The maturity scale involves 4 levels (1-4) such as minimal, development, defined, and
excellence. They defined weight for each maturity item and a scale for each dimension
to the success level of maturity, The model was developed based on two previous
380 models: IMPULS [24] and PricewaterhouseCooper’s assessment model [29].

They tested and validated the model in a focal company in the defense sector and
its 12 partners. Assessment in the focal firm was applied with 14 experts from the
organization. The result shows that the focal firm has a maturity level of 59.35 while
the sector average was 55.58. Thus, they empirically developed the model and provided
385 an analysis of major firms in the defense supply network.

A.21 Development of Maturity Model for Assessing the Implementation of Industry 4.0: Learning from Theory and Practice (M21)

Wagire et al. [51] proposed a maturity model to evaluate the "As-Is" situation of
the organization and suggest improvement areas towards Industry 4.0 transformation.
390 The model was developed based on literature review, experts' interviews, and case
studies. 15 professionals were involved in the interviews to determine the importance
level of maturity items and dimensions. The proposed model includes 38 maturity

measurement items under 7 Industry 4.0 dimensions: people and culture, Industry 4.0 awareness, organizational strategy, value chain and processes, smart manufacturing and technology, products and services-oriented technology, Industry 4.0 base technology. Each measurement item and dimension are weighted to calculate the maturity score. Each maturity item is evaluated with questions with responses on a 5-point Likert scale. The maturity score of the assessment determines the maturity level between 1 to 4: outsider, digital novice, experienced, and expert.

They employed the maturity model to assess the Industry 4.0 maturity level of a case organization in the automotive sector in India. They visited three plants and conducted interviews and 13 experts were involved in maturity assessment. They used spreadsheets to record the evaluation scores. The outcome of the assessment provided improvement opportunities for the company as the level was determined as level 2 digital novice.

A.22 A Maturity Level-Based Assessment Tool to Enhance the Implementation of Industry 4.0 in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (M22)

Rauch et al. [52] developed an assessment model to support SMEs in defining their strategy for Industry 4.0 transformation. The model was created based on a wide literature review and identification of Industry 4.0 concepts. The structure of the model consists of 4 level-1 dimensions: operations, organization, socio-culture, and technology. In the second-dimension level, there are 21 sub-dimensions and there is a total of 42 Industry 4.0 concepts categorized under the sub-dimensions. Maturity is assessed by 5 levels (1-5) but there is no specific name of the levels. For each level and Industry 4.0 concept, the descriptions are provided in matrices.

The assessment model was validated in a field study with 17 SME companies from different industrial sectors from Italy, Austria, Slovakia, and the USA. The case study resulted in a very low maturity level in participating companies. Participated companies found that assessment is a good exercise for thinking about the status of Industry 4.0 in their own company.

References

- [1] H. Lasi, P. Fettke, H.-G. Kemper, T. Feld, and M. Hoffmann, "Industry 4.0," *Bus. Inf. Syst. Eng.*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 239–242, 2014.
- 425 [2] A. Kiraz, O. Canpolat, C. Özkurt, and H. Taşkın, "Analysis of the factors affecting the Industry 4.0 tendency with the structural equation model and an application," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 150, p. 106911, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2020.106911.
- [3] "What is Industrie 4.0?," *Plattform Industrie 4.0*, Jul. 15, 2020.
430 <https://www.plattform-i40.de/PI40/Navigation/EN/Industrie40/WhatIsIndustrie40/what-is-industrie40.html> (accessed Jul. 15, 2020).
- [4] E. Y. Nakagawa, P. O. Antonino, F. Schnicke, T. Kuhn, and P. Liggesmeyer, "Continuous Systems and Software Engineering for Industry 4.0: A disruptive view," *Inf. Softw. Technol.*, vol. 135, p. 106562, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2021.106562.
435
- [5] P. B. Crosby, *Quality is free: The art of making quality certain*, vol. 94. McGraw-hill New York, 1979.
- [6] "ISO/IEC 33001:2015 Information technology – Process assessment," International Organization for Standardization, Standard, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/54175.html>
440
- [7] "Capability maturity model integration (CMMI SM), version 1.1," Standard, 2002.
- [8] Ö. Özcan-Top and O. Demirors, "Application of a software agility assessment model – AgilityMod in the field," *Comput. Stand. Interfaces*, vol. 62, pp. 1–16, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.csi.2018.07.002.
445
- [9] A. Cass, C. Völeker, R. Ouared, A. Dorling, L. Winzer, and J. M. Carranza, "SPICE for SPACE trials, risk analysis, and process improvement," *Softw. Process Improv. Pract.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 13–21, 2004.
- 450 [10] G. Yilmaz, A. Akcamete, and O. Demirors, "A reference model for BIM capability assessments," *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 101, pp. 245–263, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2018.10.022.
- [11] A. Tarhan, O. Turetken, and H. A. Reijers, "Business process maturity models: A systematic literature review," *Inf. Softw. Technol.*, vol. 75, pp. 122–134, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2016.01.010.
455
- [12] K. Y. Akdil, A. Ustundag, and E. Cevikcan, "Maturity and Readiness Model for Industry 4.0 Strategy," in *Industry 4.0: Managing The Digital Transformation*, A. Ustundag and E. Cevikcan, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 61–94. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-57870-5_4.
460
- [13] A. De Carolis, M. Macchi, B. Kulvatunyou, M. P. Brundage, and S. Terzi, "Maturity Models and Tools for Enabling Smart Manufacturing Systems: Comparison and Reflections for Future Developments," in *Product Lifecycle Management and the Industry of the Future*, Cham, 2017, pp. 23–35. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-72905-3_3.
465
- [14] E. Gökalp, U. Şener, and P. E. Eren, "Development of an Assessment Model for Industry 4.0: Industry 4.0-MM," in *Software Process Improvement and*

- Capability Determination*, Cham, 2017, pp. 128–142. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-67383-7_10.
- 470 [15] S. Mittal, M. A. Khan, D. Romero, and T. Wuest, “A critical review of smart manufacturing & Industry 4.0 maturity models: Implications for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs),” *J. Manuf. Syst.*, vol. 49, pp. 194–214, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jmsy.2018.10.005.
- 475 [16] A. Schumacher, S. Erol, and W. Sihn, “A maturity model for assessing Industry 4.0 readiness and maturity of manufacturing enterprises,” *Procedia Cirp*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 161–166, 2016.
- [17] L. Scremin, F. Armellini, A. Brun, L. Solar-Pelletier, and C. Beaudry, “Towards a framework for assessing the maturity of manufacturing companies in Industry 4.0 adoption,” in *Analyzing the Impacts of Industry 4.0 in Modern Business Environments*, IGI Global, 2018, pp. 224–254.
- 480 [18] R. Anderl, A. Picard, Y. Wang, and J. Fleischer, “Guideline Industrie 4.0 – Guiding principles for the implementation of Industrie 4.0 in small and medium sized businesses,” VDMA Forum Industrie 4.0.
- [19] J. Ganzarain and N. Errasti, “Three stage maturity model in SME’s toward industry 4.0,” *J. Ind. Eng. Manag. JIEM*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 1119–1128, 2016.
- 485 [20] R. Geissbauer, J. Vedso, and S. Schrauf, “Industry 4.0: Building the Digital Enterprise: 2016 Global Industry 4.0 Survey,” PricewaterhouseCoopers, Munich, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/industries/industries-4.0/landing-page/industry-4.0-building-your-digital-enterprise-april-2016.pdf>
- 490 [21] K. Jung, B. Kulvatunyou, S. Choi, and M. P. Brundage, “An Overview of a Smart Manufacturing System Readiness Assessment,” in *Advances in Production Management Systems. Initiatives for a Sustainable World*, Cham, 2016, pp. 705–712. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-51133-7_83.
- 495 [22] S. M. Kannan *et al.*, “Towards industry 4.0: Gap analysis between current automotive MES and industry standards using model-based requirement engineering,” in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Software Architecture Workshops (ICSAW)*, 2017, pp. 29–35.
- [23] J. Lee, S. Jun, T.-W. Chang, and J. Park, “A Smartness Assessment Framework for Smart Factories Using Analytic Network Process,” *Sustainability*, vol. 9, no. 5, Art. no. 5, May 2017, doi: 10.3390/su9050794.
- 500 [24] K. Lichtblau, V. Stich, and R. Bertenrath, “IMPULS-Industrie 4.0-Readiness,” Impuls-Stiftung des VDMA, Aachen-Köln, 2015. [Online]. Available: [http://www.impuls-](http://www.impuls-stiftung.de/documents/3581372/4875835/Industrie+4.0+Readiness+IMPULS+Studie+Oktober+2015.pdf/447a6187-9759-4f25-b186-b0f5eac69974)
- 505 [stiftung.de/documents/3581372/4875835/Industrie+4.0+Readiness+IMPULS+Studie+Oktober+2015.pdf/447a6187-9759-4f25-b186-b0f5eac69974](http://www.impuls-stiftung.de/documents/3581372/4875835/Industrie+4.0+Readiness+IMPULS+Studie+Oktober+2015.pdf/447a6187-9759-4f25-b186-b0f5eac69974)
- [25] J. Qin, Y. Liu, and R. Grosvenor, “A categorical framework of manufacturing for industry 4.0 and beyond,” *Procedia Cirp*, vol. 52, pp. 173–178, 2016.
- [26] G. Schuh, R. Anderl, J. Gausemeier, M. ten Hompel, and W. Wahlster, “Industrie 4.0 maturity index,” *Manag. Digit. Transform. Co. Munich Herbert Utz*, 2017.
- 510 [27] Rockwell Automation, “The Connected Enterprise Maturity Model,” *Rockwell Automation*, 2014.

- 515 <http://literature.rockwellautomation.com/idc/groups/literature/documents/wp/cie-wp002-en-p.pdf>
- [28] S. Weyer, M. Schmitt, M. Ohmer, and D. Gorecky, "Towards Industry 4.0 - Standardization as the crucial challenge for highly modular, multi-vendor production systems," *IFAC-Pap.*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 579–584, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2015.06.143.
- 520 [29] PwC, *Industry 4.0-Enabling Digital Operations Self Assessment*. 2016.
- [30] C. Leyh, K. Bley, T. Schäffer, and S. Forstehäusler, "SIMMI 4.0 - a maturity model for classifying the enterprise-wide it and software landscape focusing on Industry 4.0," in *2016 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems (FedCSIS)*, Sep. 2016, pp. 1297–1302.
- 525 [31] K. Menon, H. Kärkkäinen, and L. A. Lasrado, "Towards a Maturity Modeling Approach for the Implementation of Industrial Internet.," in *Pacis*, 2016, p. 38.
- [32] O. R. Yürüm, O. Demirörs, and F. Rabhi, "A Comprehensive Evaluation of Agile Maturity Self-assessment Surveys," in *Software Process Improvement and Capability Determination*, Cham, 2018, pp. 300–315. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-00623-5_21.
- 530 [33] D. Brandl, "MESA MOM Capability Maturity Model Version 1.0," *White Pap.*, vol. 53, 2016.
- [34] A. De Carolis, M. Macchi, E. Negri, and S. Terzi, "A Maturity Model for Assessing the Digital Readiness of Manufacturing Companies," in *Advances in Production Management Systems. The Path to Intelligent, Collaborative and Sustainable Manufacturing*, Cham, 2017, pp. 13–20. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-66923-6_2.
- 535 [35] G. Lanza, P. Nyhuis, S. M. Ansari, T. Kuprat, and C. Liebrecht, "Empowerment and Implementation Strategies for Industry 4.0," *ZWF Z. Für Wirtsch. Fabr.*, vol. 111, no. 1–2, pp. 76–79, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.3139/104.111462.
- 540 [36] T. Hacaloğlu and O. Demirörs, "Challenges of using software size in agile software development: A systematic literature review," *Acad. Pap. IWSM Mensura 2018*, 2018.
- 545 [37] V. Garousi, K. Petersen, and B. Ozkan, "Challenges and best practices in industry-academia collaborations in software engineering: A systematic literature review," *Inf. Softw. Technol.*, vol. 79, pp. 106–127, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2016.07.006.
- 550 [38] "Maturity assessment and maturity models in health care: A multivocal literature review - Ayça Kolukısa Tarhan, Vahid Garousi, Oktay Turetken, Mehmet Söylemez, Sonia Garossi, 2020." <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2055207620914772> (accessed Dec. 19, 2021).
- 555 [39] A. Dikici, O. Turetken, and O. Demirors, "Factors influencing the understandability of process models: A systematic literature review," *Inf. Softw. Technol.*, vol. 93, pp. 112–129, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2017.09.001.

- 560 [40] V. Garousi and M. V. Mäntylä, “A systematic literature review of literature reviews in software testing,” *Inf. Softw. Technol.*, vol. 80, pp. 195–216, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2016.09.002.
- [41] B. Kitchenham, “Procedures for performing systematic reviews,” *Keele UK Keele Univ.*, vol. 33, no. 2004, Art. no. 2004, 2004.
- 565 [42] J. Webster and R. T. Watson, “Analyzing the Past to Prepare for the Future: Writing a Literature Review,” *MIS Q.*, vol. 26, no. 2, Art. no. 2, 2002.
- [43] V. Garousi, M. Felderer, and M. V. Mäntylä, “The need for multivocal literature reviews in software engineering: complementing systematic literature reviews with grey literature,” in *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering*, New York, NY, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 1–6. doi: 570 10.1145/2915970.2916008.
- [44] C. Wohlin, “Guidelines for snowballing in systematic literature studies and a replication in software engineering,” in *Proceedings of the 18th international conference on evaluation and assessment in software engineering*, 2014, pp. 575 1–10.
- [45] A. P. T. Pacchini, W. C. Lucato, F. Facchini, and G. Mummolo, “The degree of readiness for the implementation of Industry 4.0,” *Comput. Ind.*, vol. 113, p. 103125, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.compind.2019.103125.
- [46] E. D. B. Singapore, “The Singapore smart industry readiness index,” *Catal. Transform. Manuf.*, 2018.
- 580 [47] X. Shi, T. Baba, D. Osagawa, M. Fujishima, and T. Ito, “A Maturity Model for Sustainable System Implementation in the Era of Smart Manufacturing,” in *2019 24th IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, Sep. 2019, pp. 1649–1652. doi: 585 10.1109/ETFA.2019.8869446.
- [48] S. Mittal, D. Romero, and T. Wuest, “Towards a Smart Manufacturing Maturity Model for SMEs (SM3E),” in *Advances in Production Management Systems. Smart Manufacturing for Industry 4.0*, Cham, 2018, pp. 155–163. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-99707-0_20.
- 590 [49] M. Colli, U. Berger, M. Bockholt, O. Madsen, C. Møller, and B. V. Wæhrens, “A maturity assessment approach for conceiving context-specific roadmaps in the Industry 4.0 era,” *Annu. Rev. Control*, vol. 48, pp. 165–177, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.arcontrol.2019.06.001.
- [50] L. Bibby and B. Dehe, “Defining and assessing industry 4.0 maturity levels – case of the defence sector,” *Prod. Plan. Control*, vol. 29, no. 12, pp. 1030–1043, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1080/09537287.2018.1503355.
- 595 [51] A. A. Wagire, R. Joshi, A. P. S. Rathore, and R. Jain, “Development of maturity model for assessing the implementation of Industry 4.0: learning from theory and practice,” *Prod. Plan. Control*, vol. 0, no. 0, pp. 1–20, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1080/09537287.2020.1744763.
- 600 [52] E. Rauch, M. Unterhofer, R. A. Rojas, L. Gualtieri, M. Woschank, and D. T. Matt, “A Maturity Level-Based Assessment Tool to Enhance the Implementation of Industry 4.0 in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises,” *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 9, Art. no. 9, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.3390/su12093559.

- 605 [53] M. Staples and M. Niazi, "Systematic review of organizational motivations for adopting CMM-based SPI," *Inf. Softw. Technol.*, vol. 50, no. 7, pp. 605–620, Jun. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2007.07.003.
- [54] H. Cañas, J. Mula, M. Díaz-Madroñero, and F. Campuzano-Bolarín, "Implementing Industry 4.0 Principles," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, p. 107379, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2021.107379.
- 610 [55] T. C. Lacerda and C. G. von Wangenheim, "Systematic literature review of usability capability/maturity models," *Comput. Stand. Interfaces*, vol. 55, pp. 95–105, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.csi.2017.06.001.
- [56] O. E. Adali, Ö. Ö. Top, and O. Demirörs, "Assessment of Agility in Software Organizations with a Web-Based Agility Assessment Tool," in *2017 43rd Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA)*, Aug. 2017, pp. 88–95. doi: 10.1109/SEAA.2017.61.
- 615 [57] MESA, "MESA Manufacturing Operation Management Maturity Assessment Tool," *NIST*, Mar. 21, 2019. <https://www.nist.gov/services-resources/software/mesa-manufacturing-operation-management-maturity-assessment-tool> (accessed Jul. 15, 2020).
- [58] A. De Carolis, M. Macchi, E. Negri, and S. Terzi, "Guiding manufacturing companies towards digitalization a methodology for supporting manufacturing companies in defining their digitalization roadmap," in *2017 International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Innovation (ICE/ITMC)*, Jun. 2017, pp. 487–495. doi: 10.1109/ICE.2017.8279925.
- 625 [59] S. R. Hamidi, A. A. Aziz, S. M. Shuhidan, A. A. Aziz, and M. Mokhsin, "SMEs Maturity Model Assessment of IR4.0 Digital Transformation," in *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Kansei Engineering and Emotion Research 2018*, Singapore, 2018, pp. 721–732. doi: 10.1007/978-981-10-8612-0_75.
- 630 [60] C. Leyh, T. Schäffer, K. Bley, and S. Forstehäusler, "Assessing the IT and Software Landscapes of Industry 4.0-Enterprises: The Maturity Model SIMMI 4.0," in *Information Technology for Management: New Ideas and Real Solutions*, Cham, 2017, pp. 103–119. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-53076-5_6.
- 635 [61] E. Söderström and F. Meier, "Combined SOA Maturity Model (CSOAMM): Towards a Guide for SOA Adoption," in *Enterprise Interoperability II*, London, 2007, pp. 389–400. doi: 10.1007/978-1-84628-858-6_43.
- [62] V. Zeller, C. Hocken, and V. Stich, "acatech Industrie 4.0 Maturity Index – A Multidimensional Maturity Model," in *Advances in Production Management Systems. Smart Manufacturing for Industry 4.0*, Cham, 2018, pp. 105–113. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-99707-0_14.
- 640 [63] W. D. Lin, M. Y. H. Low, Y. T. Chong, and C. L. Teo, "Application of SIRI for Industry 4.0 Maturity Assessment and Analysis," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)*, Dec. 2019, pp. 1450–1454. doi: 10.1109/IEEM44572.2019.8978720.
- 645